

SHACLE validation for the OEKG

Table 1. IRI and label of entities (nodes and edges) that are validated via the shape graph. Depending on the type, the entities are checked for the correct data type, range, minimum and maximum cardinality as well as for correct outgoing edges from certain nodes (classes or target nodes of relations).

IRI	label	data type	range	min. cardinality	max. cardinality	outgoing edges
nodes / classes						
OEO_00020227	scenario bundle					X
OEO_00020012	study report					X
OEO_00000365	scenario factsheet					X
OEO_00000172	framework factsheet					X
OEO_00000277	model factsheet					X
rdfs:label		X		X	X	
dc:acronym		X		X	X	
dc:abstract		X			X	
edges / relations						
OEO_00390071	has study descriptor tag		X	X		X
BFO_0000051	has part		X			
OEO_00390079	based_on_sector_division		X	X		X
OEO_00020439	covers sector (shortcut)		X	X		X
OEO_00020438	covers technology (shortcut)		X	X		X
OEO_00000508	has_contact_person		X			X
OEO_00000510	has_organisation		X			X
OEO_00000509	has_funding_source		X			X
OEO_00020432	covers energy carrier (shortcut)		X			X
OEO_00390095	has uuid	X		X	X	
OEO_00000506	has_author		X	X		X
OEO_00390096	has publication date	X		X	X	
OEO_00390098	has doi	X			X	
OEO_00390073	has scenario type		X	X		X
OEO_00020222	has interacting region		X			X
OEO_00020220	has study region		X			X
OEO_00020440	has scenario year value	X				
OEO_00020437	has information input (shortcut)		X			X
OEO_00020436	has information output (shortcut)		X			X
OEO_00390094	has iri	X			X	
oekg:has_id		X			X	

Table 2. Accumulated violations of the SHACL constraints of the OEKG with respect to shape and entity. All violations occur due to missing entries.

Missing entry for			
shape	IRI	label	occurrences
Study shape	OEO_00390071	has study descriptor tag	2
	OEO_00390079	based on sector division	13
	OEO_00020439	covers sector (shortcut)	16
	OEO_00020438	covers technology (shortcut)	13
Publication shape	OEO_00000506	has author	4
	OEO_00390096	has publication date	2
Scenario shape	OEO_00390073	has scenario type	5